

THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON HUMAN RESOURCES - CAREER FORMATION

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Abstract

Purpose - “the social responsibility” of the organization must include measures such as: stimulating the lifelong learning process, meaning “lifelong learning”, giving decision-making responsibility to employees (delegation and participatory management), transparency and good information throughout the organization, a sustainable and general balance between work objectives or tasks and personal and / or family needs etc.

Methodology/approach – online questionnaire used to collect the data, which allowed the analysis and explanation of the causal relationships between the variables.

Findings - corporate social responsibility must include measures of transparency and good information throughout the company, a sustainable and general balance between objectives or work tasks but also measures for employees by providing equal treatment, a sustainable and equitable structure.

Research limitations/implications - Romanian employees' interest in corporate social responsibility reports, their perception of the reasons for companies' involvement in such activities

Practical implications - real support in making managerial decisions, thus bringing a series of contributions to the CSR activity of companies

Originality/value - no Romanian research has been conducted to bring in the way employees perceive the CSR activities carried out and communicated by companies

Key words - CSR,

Introduction

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become a mass issue, gaining the status of corporate priority for the management and for the marketing of a company. The concept of CSR enjoys a not very long but varied history since more and more organizations are beginning to realize that they can contribute to a sustainable development if they conduct their operations in such a way as to achieve economic growth and competitiveness while ensuring environmental protection and promoting social responsibility, including the protection of consumer interests.

Literature review

Corporate social responsibility is a concept that has been given a lot of attention, especially in recent years, both in the literature, by reflecting it in countless scientific studies and in practice, by including it frequently in the organizational strategies and policies (Amujo et. al., 2012).

Despite numerous efforts to draft a clear and unambiguous definition of the concept, there is still some confusion, both among theorists and practitioners, as to how the social responsibility of organizations should be defined (Brown&Deegan, 1998), (Falck&Heblich, 2007), (Mohr&Webb, 2005).

This situation can be explained in terms of at least three essential aspects. First, the concept in question is very broad and complex, including a wide range of elements of a socio-economic or ecological nature, and respectively, referring to various groups of stakeholders (investors, customers, employees, suppliers, distributors, community, public authorities etc.). Second, the diversification and even abundance of definitions of social responsibility of organizations is due to the often subjective and biased

manner, determined by certain specific interests, through which those involved approach the concept and define it. Last but not least, "corporate social responsibility is in itself a dynamic phenomenon, whose meanings evolve over time and adapt to the new expectations of society." (Carrol, 1999)

The public, civil society are convinced that it is no longer enough for an organization to claim that "its only concern is to make profits for shareholders, as long as they are based on operations that fundamentally affect - negatively or positively - the lives of companies in which operates" (Ilieş, 2012)

More and more organizations are beginning to realize that they can contribute to sustainable development if they conduct their operations in such a way as to achieve economic growth and competitiveness while ensuring environmental protection and promoting social responsibility, including the protection of consumer interests. The key terms that materialize the model of social responsibility of the organization differ from one sector to another, and from organization to organization, but a generic model of corporate social responsibility include the following directions: human rights; working conditions in the supply chain, but also within the organization; the environmental impact of operations, processes, services and / or products; the impact on local communities of operations, processes, services and / or products, the impact on customers of operations, processes, services and / or products; investment responsibility) (Iamandi, 2010).

Purpose of the study

For many modern companies, a major challenge is attracting and retaining highly qualified employees. In this context, "the social responsibility" of the organization must include measures such as: stimulating the lifelong learning process, meaning "lifelong learning", giving decision-making responsibility to employees (delegation and participatory management), transparency and good information throughout the organization, a sustainable and general balance between work objectives or tasks and personal and / or family needs etc. Starting from the idea that in Romania no research has been conducted to bring in the way employees perceive the CSR activities carried out and communicated by companies, we transform this issue for the purpose of this research, extending it to research the influence of corporate social responsibility on career formation.

Characteristic of contemporary society is the assumption that at work, in performing tasks, each employee behaves in a conscious and responsible manner. Being a good citizen now means appreciating values, behaving responsibly and morally, helping to maintain a clean environment, and having decent interpersonal relationships, requirements that apply to companies, but also to their employees.

It is important to know within an organization / company how satisfied / dissatisfied the employees are, because if an employee is satisfied it means that he is: more motivated and easier to get involved in new projects, he has fewer absences due to illness or for other reasons, he is more loyal, less inclined to leave the company, indispensable in difficult times, he is more productive, more responsible for a good working atmosphere. While a dissatisfied employee is less motivated, has a poor professional performance, has many absences due to illness, does not perform his tasks, affects team spirit, does not communicate very well.

My research considers employees' perceptions of the influence of social responsibility in career formation. We drafted a research model of corporate social responsibility, whereby correlating with the internal and external dimensions and actions of corporate social responsibility we identified the fact that there are several ways to determine the perception of company employees. Thus, managers can choose between direct conversations with employees, group discussions or questionnaires depending on the organizational culture of the company, structure, organization and even the atmosphere at work.

Another objective of the present study is to identify factors influencing the response of social responsibility in career formation. Employees have the right for the company they work for to show them the impact of their social responsibility activities, because only if they see how important and significant the company's CSR strategies are, employees can become more satisfied, more devoted to it, fact which also emerges from the research model of corporate social responsibility.

Methodology and sample data

The experimental data were subjected to processing, using the hypothetical-deductive theoretical method for interpreting, and explaining the results, as well as methods of quantitative and qualitative interpretation with differentiation of characteristics for distinct experimental groups.

We have chosen this method of collecting data in this research, namely the combination of qualitative and quantitative because this offers a high degree of validity and credibility to the research results, while allowing the exploration of the research topic from several perspectives.

The online questionnaire was used to collect the data, which allowed the analysis and explanation of the causal relationships between the variables. A modern method of applying the questionnaire was used, namely its online design and application, using the Google Forms application, and the final data were processed using the Excel 2019 program.

The sample considered in this research is represented by people between 18 and 45 years old who are in career training, domiciled in Romania in 2022, and who are internet users (thus being able to access the questionnaire in this case). I received 25 valid questionnaires applied, which allowed me to verify the validity of the questionnaires by statistical techniques.

Following the analysis of the level of education of the respondents shows that the majority (48%) of the respondents have a bachelor's degree, while 32% of them have secondary education. Only 12% of respondents have master's degrees and 8% have doctoral studies. Considering the age, 48% of the respondents are between 18 and 25 years old, 40% are between 26 and 35 years old and 12% are over 35 years old. We had 60% male respondents and 40% female respondents. In terms of the field of activity of the companies 24% are companies in the field of trade / retail, 20% services, 12% education, 12% banking / financial services, 12% IT / Telecom, 8% transport, 4% tourism, 4% agricultural, 4% legal.

Most respondents (46%) work in large companies (51-250 employees), followed by those who work in medium-sized companies (26 - 50 employees) in proportion of 23%, 15% work in a multinational company, 12 % in small companies (11 0 25 employees) and only 4% work in a micro-enterprise (maximum 10 employees). Most of the 25 respondents (84%) claim they work in companies that have implemented CSR activities, while 12% say that in their companies no CSR activities are performed and 1 (4%) does not have knowledge of the existence of such CSR activities.

Findings and results

Most respondents agree that human resources management represents one of the internal dimensions of corporate social responsibility. So most of the respondents agree with the fact that the social responsibility of the company must include measures regarding transparency and good information at each level of the whole company, a sustainable and general balance between objectives or work tasks and personal and/or family needs, payments and opportunities of equal career opportunities, the active promotion of employees in a situation of inactivity due to permanent/temporary illnesses/disabilities, but also with the fact that the company must present a model for employees by granting equal treatment, a sustainable and fair structure.

According to the respondents the management of the impact on the environment and natural resources is one of the internal dimensions of corporate social responsibility, which is based on the following logical connection: reducing the consumption of resources and reducing polluting emissions and waste can reduce the impact on the environment. Most respondents agreed that the sustainable development (items q21 – q22) represents a process that has identified complex community problems such as the incorrect use of natural resources. Corporate social responsibility being seen from this point of view as a potential solution for solving gender issues by integrating it into the organization's business strategy. Globalization (items q23 – q24), according to respondents' statements, also represents one of the CSR actions, for CSR plays a vital role in detecting the impact that globally expanded businesses have on the workforce, on the local community and its economy (see figure no. 1).

Figure no. 1 – CSR Actions

Corporate social responsibility can provide viable solutions to ensure the public good. Regarding governance (items q25 – q26), respondents agreed with the statement that CSR provides internationally accepted tools regarding human rights, the environment and anti-corruption. Most respondents stated that the actions of the corporate sector (q27) represent a CSR action due to the way companies behave, which has become an issue of general interest because their influence on the political, social, and environmental systems is increasing. According to the agreement of most respondents, information and communication technology offers increased possibilities for internal and/or external communication for any company, and in the context of CSR, information and communication technologies offer the chance to improve strategic partnerships and social dialogue. Regarding another CSR action, namely financial capital (items q30 – q31), most respondents stated that they agree/strongly agree with the statement that CSR can help build value and better responsiveness from the part of those interested in the business. According to most respondents, the ethical actions (items q32 – q34) represent a CSR action, because an approach to CSR from this point of view can lead to the improvement of the company's relationship with the interested groups, to greater transparency and to ethical standards raised. Leadership (items q35 – q36), represents another action of CSR, and according to respondents' opinions, CSR offers the chance to act in those areas where provisions seem unlikely. The last CSR action is represented by the business tools (items q37 – q39), which according to the answers received from the respondents, with the adoption of some effective social responsibility programs, they can reduce the risk of business division, and can lead to new opportunities, innovations, brand growth and even improving work efficiency.

Regarding the research on CSR awareness among company employees (figure no. 2), most respondents agreed with the following: in the adoption of CSR strategies, the HR department plays an important role (14), employees can manage the implementation of CSR strategies (12), employees can

proactively monitor the adoption of CSR strategies while documenting its success throughout the company (18), CSR has a high effect on attracting, motivating and/or retaining an employee (15), certain employees work for a socially responsible company, because it can offer them opportunities for promotion, professional development (10), employees are inspired to work more, to be more productive, when they work for a socially responsible company (10). We can see from figure no. 3, that even if there were respondents who did not agree, or who did not want to express themselves (neither agreement nor disagreement), the majority agreed/totally agreed with the statements regarding how employees perceive the influence of CSR in career training, so most agreed with statements such as: the existence and compliance of the internal order regulation by employees (18), transparency in a company must be manifested by honesty towards employees (18), employees they must be informed in a fair and coherent way regarding the CSR strategies undertaken by the company (15), etc.

Figure no. 2 - Awareness of CSR by the company's employees

Figure no. 3 - Employees' perception of the influence of CSR in career formation

Discussion and conclusions

The research aimed to determine employees' perceptions regarding the activities and policies of corporate social responsibility implemented by companies, and their influence in career formation, by identifying employees' expectations in this regard, the way they perceive the components of CSR, by identifying the degree of involvement and the influence of CSR on career formation.

From a practical point of view, the results obtained in this research can provide real support in managerial decision-making, thus bringing a series of contributions for the CSR activity of companies. So, for example, it could help company managers to find the necessary justification to invest in the development of CSR strategies, investments that can create, in the long term, effects both on the company, but also on the employees, such as trust, satisfaction, loyalty, high degree of productivity, devotion to the company.

At the same time, it can offer company managers a starting point in the form of an answer to the questions: CSR represents a cost for the company or a long-term investment and what are the expectations and how employees perceive the CSR activities that the company wants to implement.

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